

UTILIZATION OF SPIRITUAL CARE AMONG NURSES OF FEDERAL PSYCHIATRIC HOSPITAL CALABAR

Rosaline Ekpenyong Esen

rosalineesen@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Spiritual nursing care is integrative, one cannot separate spirituality from the physical, social or emotional aspects of self. For patients spiritual nursing care should promote integration of all aspects of a patient's life through the discovery of meaning amid life's circumstance. The study was carried out to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of spiritual care by Nurses in Federal Psychiatric Hospital — Calabar. The study was carried out to enlighten the Nurses on the nature of man, nature of nursing and place of spiritual care in nursing practice. To also provide useful information to the readers on the importance of utilizing spiritual care to achieve quality care delivery. The design adopted for the study was descriptive survey. Cluster sampling technique was use group nurses into wards and systematic sampling technique to select 32 nurses that were used for the study. Five research questions and 4 hypotheses guided the study and questionnaire was used in the collection of data. Analysis of data was done using tables and percentages. Hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment correlation(r) as measure. Findings revealed that the level of knowledge was good on spiritual nursing care, attitude of nurses towards spiritual care was unfavourable, The frequency of utilization of spiritual care was poor despite the perceived positive outcome on the patient. It also revealed that if the belief system of the patient contradicts the nurses own, spiritual care is not practicable. Association relations revealed a significant relationship between attitude and the extent of utilization of spiritual care. And a significant influence between practice and outcome on patients and family members. In view of the above findings, it was recommended that spiritual care be emphasized in the training school to equip the nurses and the hospital authority should have a clergy man within the hospital to attain to the spiritual needs of patients.

KEYWORDS: Spiritual care, Nurses, Utilization, and Federal psychiatric hospital Calabar

INTRODUCTION

Spiritual care is an intuitive, interpersonal, altruistic and integrative expression. It is contingent on the nurses awareness of the transcendent dimension of life that reflects the patient's reality. It is an expression of self, the way of love, a life live out in the relationship of care. (Sawatzky; Pesut, 2001). It involves spiritual expression such as love, hope and compassion by the nurses to their patients. Spiritual care begins from a perspective of being with the patient. Showing love to him or her and communicating as well. These may be therapeutic to the patient. Such intervention that take direction from the patient's religious or spiritual life to some extent assist the patient towards return to normal behaviour.

For the nurse to render spiritual care, she must have transcendent, that is surpassing awareness which is developed within the context of a relationship with a "Divine being or ultimate reality or ultimate truth as percent by the individual", (Larson et all 1998). It involves being a perpetual learner in spiritual things nurses avoid spiritual care because of the feeling of insecurity in their own spiritual lives. They rather assign less values and importance to spiritual care. They believe that it is the clergy's duty and that they as nurses have inadequate education on spiritual matters to provide spiritual care. As such they prefer not to dabble into it.

The need to practice spiritual care in federal psychiatric Hospital by nurses cannot be overemphasized because mental illness is very often attributed by patients and their relations to offense against God, violation of cultural believes, affliction from evil spirits, possession by an evil spirit, activities of wit- craft stealing from the gods, taking false oath, and punishment for the sins of the parents. Many a times these patients are taken to either churches or spiritual homes or occultic places before coming to the hospital. All these precipitate a spiritual crisis in the patients and the family because of the fear of the unknown and feeling of helplessness, which make them move aware from the need to rely on God. During these period patients do not exhibit normal behaviour but rather exhibit abnormal behaviour. They are isolated from other members and cannot participate fully and adequately in activities within the fold, these make them feel cut off from the fold.

Spiritual care therefore is an essential part of the healing process because it ensures spiritual wellbeing which is an indicator of spiritual health and relates significantly with self-esteem, hope and recovery during illness. Human is made up of the body, soul and spirit which are interdependent and interrelated. What affects one part affects the rest. Because of this spiritual nature, man must have a harmonious, positive relationship with his creator to be able to function well. Total health of man entails treating the body, and treating the spirit. Therefore, the nurse should give care in a holistic manner that incorporates awareness of the clients' spiritual needs.

Based on these the researcher wishes to find out the attitude and practice of spiritual

care by nurses in federal psychiatric hospital-Calabar. Most current mental health care delivery system are diagnosis and treatment oriented. Traditionally, most people receive mental health care only after the onset of behavioural signs and symptoms. Many a times such persons get to a health facility when they are in an acute or chronic state, that are more difficult and expensive to manage. Emphasis was rarely on prevention or early diagnosis as we have now a days. Over the years health care models had been developed to recognize the inter-relatedness of mind, body and environment known as holism. This concept helps to blend many aspects of mental health care. The primary goal of nurses and other mental health care providers is to help clients develop strategies to achieve harmong with themselves and with others, nature and the world.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the impact nurses attitude create towards spiritual care of patents in federal psychiatric hospital-Calabar
2. To examine the influence of spiritual care on psychiatric patients and their families members

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant relationship between Nurses attitude to spiritual care and the extent to which spiritual care is utilized in their nursing practice.
2. The practice of spiritual care does not significantly influence outcomes in psychiatric patients and their families.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Knowledge of Spiritual Care

Spiritual care according to John (2005) is the care given to a sick person to assist him establish or maintain a positive relationship with the Supreme Being. This will be evidenced by faith in God and a feeling of hope. According to her, the nurse has a duty to support and care for the whole person. Just as she assist the patient to perform physical care that he cannot do for himself. The nurse is duty bound to perform spiritual care which is often neglected during illness. According to Carvin et al (1992) in a study on knowledge of Nurses on spiritual care, the findings indicates that nurse are reluctant and uncomfortable with the spiritual aspects of care. Although patients expect it and the healing process may be affected. Nurses must recognize that spiritual assessment and interventions are within the scope of practice. The Presbyterian hospital chaplain of Dallas (2003) stated that patients have spiritual care needs when feeling fearful, hopeless, depressed or coping with anger, bitterness, quilt or trying to understand the purpose of suffering or trying to cope with stigma and discrimination.

According to Thomas (1993), Nurses may be aware that patients have spiritual needs but in many cases are unable to respond to these needs. This according to him may be as a result of an inadequacy in nurse education that does not prepare nurses to provide spiritual care. In addition, spiritual care is seen as part of the psychosocial assessment in the domain of the pastoral care workers. In a research carried out by nurses Christian fellowship to determine patient's awareness of their spiritual needs, the findings revealed that female patients verbalized more spiritual needs than males. The clergy is the preferred person whom patients speak to about spiritual needs.

Relief from fear of death, knowledge of God's presence, expression of caring and support from another person; and receiving the sacraments were ranked the first four most important spiritual needs by patients. That patients appreciated concern and kindness from nurses and desire to be allowed to talk and listened to by nurses. According to American Holistic Association (1986), Nurses should give care in a holistic manner that incorporates awareness of the client's spiritual needs. In a research carried out by Mc Robert *et al* (2000) on spiritual care A study on the views and practices of psychiatric nurses. Analysis of the data indicated that respondent reported receiving spiritual training in diverse methods with 54.5% indicating that training was done through reading about spiritual care. Other respondents 0.1% included that continuing education and special course work were methods of training in spiritual care.

Attitude of Nurses toward Spiritual Care

In a research on the topic "spiritual care: a study on the views and practices of psychiatric nurse" by MC Roberts *et al* (2000) the purpose was to assess the willingness and ability of nurses to offer spiritual care. Attitudes and belief of 33 registered nurses in a rural western state were evaluated. The nurse highest rating was referring clients to their personal energy and praying privately for their clients. The nurse lowest rating was praying with the client and reading the scriptural writings. In their conclusion it was stated that data obtained in the study indicated that there was a need for continuing education to implement the spiritual aspect of holistic nursing care to psychiatric clients.

John (1995) opined that nurses are called to be coworkers with God in the ministry of healing. Therefore, the nurse should give care in a holistic manner that cooperates awareness of the clients spiritual needs. However, despite this position spiritual care remains a neglected focus of nursing practice. The reason cited for this reluctance include fear of invading patient's privacy (John, 1995); lack of training to detect spiritual needs and provide spiritual care (Feudtner *et al*, 2003) lack of time (Doff, 1993). In a study on spiritual dimensions by psychiatric Nurses, COX (2005) reported that the purpose of the study was to examine the spiritual dimension of care. The dependent variable was practice and one of the

independent variable was attitude towards giving spiritual care. Results indicated that the attitude toward giving spiritual care was generally positive. Almost 90% of the nurses felt certain about personal spiritual beliefs and disagreed that only clergy could give spiritual care.

In a discussion on professional boundaries and prayer in the nurses' patients relationship, Post et al., (2000) proposed that Nurses may be considered coercive if they initiate prayer without first being asked by the patient. Prayer in this relationship is only acceptable if the patient is intent on prayer with a health care provider and if the health care provider can pray without having to manipulate or feign faith.

Practice of Spiritual Care (Utilization)

Spiritual care is an essential part of the healing process because it ensures spiritual well-being which is an indicator of spiritual health. It relates significantly with self-esteem, hope and recovery during illness (Mickery *et al*, 1992 and Kena, 2003). A study on Awareness and preparedness of Nurses to meet spiritual needs (Shelly and fish, (1983) revealed that 8.8% of respondents agreed that they read the Bible with the patients, 29.4% prayed with patient, 50% neither read the Bible nor prayed with the patients. None agreed that patient's spiritual need was completely met 6.1% agreed it was adequately met, 33% said it was poorly met while 3.0% said it was not met at all. Pieces of literature have shown that spiritual practice plays great roles in mental health care (1Esen & Peters, 2023; 2Esen & Peters, 2023; 3Esen & Peters, 2023 and Esen, Peters & Esen, 2023).

About 60.6% of the respondents said they will like further education to meet the spiritual needs of the patients while 39.4% opined that, they would not like further education to be able to meet the spiritual needs of the patients. Feher and Mely (199) opined that withholding spiritual care amounts to negligence. That if nurses truly embrace holistic concept of patient's care, they have an ethical obligation to provide spiritual care. According to Wright, (1998), the principle of beneficence, non-maleficence and advocacy are also applicable to spiritual care by nurses. He stated that withholding spiritual care violates these principles.

Outcomes of Spiritual Nursing Care

Nurse in Narayanasawmy and Owen's (2001) study revealed that recipients of spiritual care appeared more peaceful, relieved and calm and grateful. That patients as well as their family members expressed feelings of being comforted. Labun (1988) proposed outcomes such as tranquility, peace, and development of meaningful purposeful behaviors. According to Koenig (1997) spiritual care reduces the costs of patients care because it enhances recovery and decreases the duration of illness. Studies by Koenig et al (1998); Johnson and Spika (1991) revealed that more than half of respondents reported that spiritual

care is the most important resource that helped them cope with illness, loss and grief. A number of indicators used in evaluating spiritual nursing care were identified by Ross (1997). These include: improvements in patient's mood, an acceptance of current difficulties and verbal indication that the need had been met. Brady et al (1995), stated that spiritual care leads to improved spiritual well being which in turn improves the quality of life and general health of the patients. Pargament (1997) posited that up to 63% of people in the population believe in the healing power of spirituality to aid recovery from illness and when facing a crises people often turn to their spirituality as a means of coping.

Belief System of Nurses

Most Christians according to Shelly and John (1963:61) initially, tend to think that all talk about God is healthy and an open door to share their faith. Many non-Christian therapists believe that all talk about God and religious ideation is pathological and to be avoided. Both extremes result from a lack of understanding and experience and both can create problems in therapy. According to them imposition of religion on clients by nurses is unhealthy. Religion is healthy when it moves an individual or system toward wholeness and integration but becomes sick when it moves toward fragmentation.

Carvin et al (1992) posited that the provision of spiritual care involves the spirituality of both the nurse and his patient and its transformational for both is stressed. Considering the ethical aspect of prayer with patients, Winslow et al (2003) suggested that permission should be obtained from the patient and that permission should only be sought after the nurse has gotten information to suggest that it would be meaningful for the patient. Recent authors have proposed an existential approach to spiritual care by emphasizing the importance of dialogue (McGrath, 1997) and personal meaning (Narayamasany and Owens, 2001; Walter, 1997). Within this approach, all persons are viewed as spiritual beings. Regardless of their religious orientation (Thomason and Brady, 1999).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The model adopted for this study is Neumann's systems model and Watson's Human's caring theory which address the spiritual dimension of patients care. Newman views the client as basic structure or central core of energy resources (physiologic psychological, socio-cultural developmental and spiritual) surrounded by two concentric boundaries or rings referred to as lines of resistance. The lines of resistance represent internal factors that help the patient defend against a stressor, outside the lines of resistance are two lines of defense.

The inner or normal line of defense; depicted as a solid line represents the person's state of equilibrium or the state of adaptation developed and maintained over time and

considered for that person. The flexible line of defense, depicted as a broken line is dynamic and can be rapidly altered over a short period of time. It is a protective buffer that prevents stressors from penetrating the normal line of defense. The health practitioners uses the term physiologic, psychological, socio-cultural and spiritual to be the cause of illness can be caused by any deviation in these systems. As such nursing interventions. Focus on retaining or maintaining system stability.

Nenmans theory states that spirituality permeates all aspect f a person regardless of whether or not it is acknowledged or developed it further states that when lines pain, loss or grief strikes a person, energy is depleted and one's spirit is affected producing spiritual needs and concerns.

Note: Physiologic, Psychological developmental and spiritual variables occur and are considered simultaneously in each concentric circle.

Watson's human caring theory propounds that the practice of caring is central to nursing. It is the unifying focus for practice.

Caring involves providing a supportive, protective or corrective mental, physical socio-cultural and spiritual environment for the patient.

Her philosophy of caring propounds that nursing embraces a spiritual dimension of the caring process and is concerned with preserving human dignity.

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for this study is descriptive survey. The research setting is Federal psychiatric hospital, Calabar in Cross River State. Federal psychiatric hospital Calabar was founded by Cross River State Government in 1903 and was handed over to the Federal

Government of Nigeria in 1995. It is located in the Calabar South Local government Area of Cross River State. It is bounded in the south by Edgerly Street, North by White House Street, East by Chambly Street and Calabar road in the West. For administrative purpose, the Federal psychiatric hospital is divided into three sections as follows:

- Clinical services
- Administration

Department of internal Audit.

The chief medical director is the overall head of the organization. Each department/unit has a head. The chairman Medical Advisory Committee is the head of clinical services and training. While the director of Administration is the head of internal audit and chairman medical advisory committee and directly responsible to the chief medical director.

Nursing department is under clinical services and is headed by the Head of Nursing services.

The institution operates two programmes:

School of psychiatric nursing.

- Residency training programme.

As a tertiary health institution the activities carried out by the different departments are geared towards attainment of the following goals:

- Prevention
- Diagnosis
- Education
- Research
- Patient care
- Rehabilitation

The hospital has a total of 473 workers, out of which 90 are nurses. Distributions as follows:

Wards		61
OPC		8
Compound -		9
ECT		1
CSSD		1
Administration	2 School	8

The targeted population was 69 registered psychiatric nurses that are working in the out patient clinic (OPC) and wards. A total of 32 respondents were enrolled for this study. This was selected from the 69 registered psychiatric nurses working in OPC and the wards of Federal psychiatric hospital Calabar. Cluster sampling technique was used to group nurses into wards, systemic sampling technique was then used to select the respondents among nurses who fell into even numbers in each of the units. Distribution as follows:

Table1: Showing units, systemic sampling and percentages from each unit

Units	Number of Nurses	Sample	Percentages 0/0
OPC'	8	4	5.8
Ward 2	8	4	5.8
Ward 3	9	4	5.8
Ward 4	9	4	5.8
Ward 5	11	5	7.3
Ward 6	9	4	5.8
Ward 7	7	3	4.4
Ward 8	8	4	5.8
Total 8	69	32	46.5

Structured questionnaires was used for data collection. The questionnaire had two sections. The first part captured the socio-demographic data of the respondents. The second section-involved likert type question designed for the collection of data on the variables of interest in the study. The second part had 4 points response options ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree for each statement. The value of 4 indicated the most positive while the value of 1 represented the most negative. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher to the nurses in Federal psychiatric hospital. This was done while the nurses were on duty and completed forms were collected by the researcher from the respondents.

Data was analyzed using descriptive statistical measures (frequency tables and percentages for socio — demographic data and research questions. Association relationships were tested using inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Movement Correlation Coefficient and ANOVA.

For ethical consideration, permission was obtained from the management of federal psychiatric hospital Calabar to carry out the study. Informed consent was also obtained from respondent. The respondents were assured of strict confidentiality and privacy.

RESULT

The hypothesis guided the study and were tested using appropriate statistical techniques at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis I: There is no significant relationship between Nurses attitude to spiritual care and the extent to which spiritual care is utilized in psychiatric nursing practice.

The pearson's product moment correlation analysis technique was used in testing this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and 30 degrees of freedom. Details of results of the

correlation analysis are displayed in table 2.

Table 2: Nurses Attitudes to Spiritual Care and the extent of use of Spiritual Care in their Nursing Practice

(n=32)

Variable	Ex	Ex2 2	Exy	R	t
Nurses Attitudes	545	198.97	120.88	0.65	4.68
Use of spiritual care	548	173.50			

Significant @ 0.05; t-critical - — 2.042

The entries in table 2 indicate that the correlation between nurses attitudes and use of spiritual care is as strong as $r=0.65$. This is a strong positive relationship which is converted to its t-value equivalent to be 4.68.

Comparing this t-value to the critical t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 30 degrees of freedom. The t-calculated (4.68) is greater than t-critical (2.042).

Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative retained.

This means that there is significant relationship between nurses attitudes to spiritual care and the extent to which spiritual care is utilized in psychiatric nursing practice in Federal psychiatric hospital Calabar.

Hypothesis 2: The practice of spiritual care does not significantly influence outcomes in psychiatric patients and their families.

The one-way ANOVA technique was use to test for statistical significance at 0.05 level. Degrees of freedom used were 7 and 24. the details of the result of the test are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Influence of spiritual care on psychiatric patients and their families members (n = 32)

Source of variation	Sum of squares	dof	Mean square	F	Remark
Between groups	123.244	7	17.606	8.408	significant
Within groups	50.256	24	2.094		
Total	173.5	31			

*F- ratio is significant at 0.05 level, F — critical = 2.44

From table 3, F-ratio is 8.408 as compared to the F-critical value of 2.44. Thus null

Hypothesis is rejected in favour of its alternative.

It is therefore concluded that the practice of spiritual care does significantly influence the outcome in psychiatric patients and their families.

DISCUSSION FO FINDINGS

The purpose of the study was to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of spiritual care by Nurses in Federal Hospital, Calabar. The discussion of findings is based on the outcomes of the hypothesis and research questions that guided the study. Considering the ethical aspects of prayer with patients, Winslow *et al.*, 2003) suggested that permission should be obtained from the patient and that permission should only be sought after the nurse has information to suggest that it would be meaningful for the patient. In agreement with Shelley and John (1993) most Christians tend to think that all talk about God is health and the open door to share their faith.

Many non-Christian therapists belief that all talk about God and religion is pathological and should be avoided. Both extremes result from a lack of understanding, experience and create problem in therapy. To support Carvin *et al.*, 1992), the provision of spiritual care involves the spirituality of both the nurse and the patient. This implies that the nurse must respect the patients belief and patient consent should be obtained when spiritual care is given.

These is significant relationship between nurses attitude to spiritual care and the extent to which spiritual care is utilized in psychiatric nursing practice. The findings agrees with Cox (2005), who indicated that the attitude toward practice of spiritual care was positive. That almost 90% of the Nurses disagreed that only the clergy could give spiritual care. This implies that the value given to spiritual care in nursing practice determines the frequency of utilization of spiritual care in psychiatric nursing practice.

The practice of spiritual care does significantly influence the outcome in psychiatric patients and their family members. According to Brady *et al.*, 1995), the practice of spiritual care leads to improvement in the wellbeing of the psychiatric patients which in turn improves the quality of life and general health of the patient. The implication of this result is for the encouragement of spiritual care in psychiatric nursing practice, as the impact of discrimination and stigmatization could be very devastating. Spiritual care comes on hand to help both psychiatric patients and their family members cope with the post traumatic syndromes of mental disorder.

CONCLUSIONS

Spiritual care should be utilized along side with scientific nursing care to achieve holistic nursing care of psychiatric patients in the Federal psychiatric hospital Calabar. This

is because human beings etc made up of the physical, social, mental and spiritual component and spiritual care is necessary to meet the spiritual needs of the patient.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings in this study, the following recommendations are made.

1. Spiritual care should be emphasized on the training school to equip the nurses to be able to utilize it in the care of psychiatric patients.
2. Nurses should include spiritual care while drawing up a nursing care plan to ensure the spiritual needs of the patients are met.
3. The patient's belief should be respected to encourage the patients to accept spiritual care.
4. More research on the value of spiritual care and practice should be carried out to add to the body of nursing research.

REFERENCES

- Brady, M.J. Peterman, A. H. Fitchet, G. M. M. & Celia, D. (1999). A case study for including spirituality in quality of life measurement in Oncology. *Psycho-oncology*, 6(5); 417-428.
- Cox, E. E. (2005). Spiritual interventions by Psychiatric Nurses. Intervarsity Christian fellowship USA. Web servant at Intervarsity/Org. Member of the international fellowship of Evangelical students.
- Dorff, E. (1993). Religion at a Time of Crisis: Quality of life: a nursing challenge. *Spiritual wellbeing*, 2(3); 56-59.
- Esen, R. E., Peters, M. I. & Esen, Ubongabasi Akpan (2023), Divination and Mental Health Seeking Behaviour of the Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria: A Qualitative Exploration. *International Journal of Culture and Society* Zenodo, Switzerland, Maiden Edition (1): 18–29
- ¹Esen, R. E. & Peters, M. I. (2023). Mental Illness and The Panacea of Orthodox Medicine Patronage Among Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities* (GJCH). Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 2(1): 2-16
- ²Esen, R. E. & Peters, M. I. (2023). Herbalists and Mental Health Seeking Behaviour among the Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria. *Social Sciences and Management International Journal* Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 4(1): 1-14.
- ³Esen, R. E. & Peters, M. I. (2023). Faith Healing and Mental Illness among Ibibio People. *Ripple of Culture: Journal of Anthropology*. 2(1): 50–63.
- Feher, S & Maly, C. (1999). Coping with breast cancer in later life. The Role of Religious faith, *Psycho Oncology*, 8(5), 408-416.
- Fish, Sharon, and Judith Allen Shelly. (1978) *Spiritual care: The Nurses Role*. Downers

Grove, IL: Intervarsity press.

- Fitchet, G. (1999). Selected Resources for screening for spiritual Ristks. *Chaplainal Today*, 15(1); 13-26.
- Fitchet, G; Rybarczyk, BD. Demarco, G. A. & Nicholas, J.J. (1999). The Role of Religion in medical Rehabilitation outcomes: a longitudinal study. *Rehabilitation psychology*, 44(4); 333353.
- Goldberg, B. (1998). Connection: An exploration of spirituality in nursing care. *Journal of advanced Nursing*, 27, 836-842.
- Hall, B.A. (1997). Spirituality in terminal illness: An alternative view of theory. *Journal of Holistic Nursing*, 15, 82-96.
- John, M.E. (1995). Need for spiritual care in nursing: an opinion survey. *Proceedings of the 3rd Binnial conference of Association of Religion and spirituality in medicine*, 21-28.
- John, M.E. (1998). Spiritual care in hospitals: a necessary aspect *journal of Nursing*, 9 (2); 109-113.
- Kenedrick, K.D. & Robinson, S. (2000) Spirituality: Its relevance and purpose for clinical nursing in a new millennium. *Journal of clinical Nursing*, 9, 701-705.
- King, D.E. & Bushwick, B. (1994). Beliefs and attitudes of hospitalized inpatients about faith healing and prayer. *Journal of family practice*, 39;349-352.
- Koenig, H.G. (1997). Use of Religion by patients with several medical illness mind/body medicine, 2; 31-36.
- Koenig, H.G; Pargament R.I. & Nielson, J. (1998). Religion coping and Health Statutes in medically ill hospitalized older adults. *Journal of Narvous & mental disease*, 186 (9); 513-521.
- Labun, E. (1988). Spiritual care: An element in nursing care planning. *Journey of Advanced nursing*, 13, 314-320.
- Lane, J.A. (1987). The care of the human spirit, *journal of professional nursing*, 3 , 332-337.
- Larson, D.B, Sawyers, J.P, & M.C. Cullough, M.E. (1998). *Scientific research on spirituality and health: A report based on the scientific progress in spirituality conferences*, New York: John M. Templeton Foundation.
- Lena, M. (2004), spiritual care: essential part of healing. [Hhp//www.spiritual care.html](http://www.spiritualcare.html). retrieved 26/03/04.
- McGrath, P. (1997). Putting spirituality on the agenda: Hospice research findings on the ignored dimension, *Hospice journal*, 12(4), 1-13.
- Narayanasamy, A. & Owens, J. (2001). A critical incident study of nurses' responses to the spiritual needs of their patients. *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 33, 446-455.

- O'Brien, M.E. (1999). *Spirituality in nursing: standing on holy ground*. Sudbury, MA: Jones and Bartlett.
- Pargament, K. (1997). *A psychology of religion and caring: theory, Research, practice*. New York, Guilford publishers.
- Piles, C. (1990), providing spiritual care. *Nurse Educator*, 36-43.
- Post, S.G., Puchalski, C.M; & Larson, D.B. (2000). Physicians and patient spirituality: professional boundaries, competency and ethics. *Annals of internal medicine* 132, 578-583.
- Price, J.L, Stevens, H.O., & Labarre, M.C. (1995). *Spiritual Journal of psychosocial Nursing*, 33, (12), 5-9.
- Rew, L. (1989). Intuition: Nursing knowledge and the spiritual dimension of persons. *holistic Nursing practice*, 3(3), 56-68.
- Ross, L. (1994). Spiritual aspects of nursing. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 19, 439-447.
- Sivan, A. Fichet, G. & Burton, L. (1996). Hospitalized Psychiatric and medical patients and the clergy, *journal of Religion & Health*, 35 (1); 11-19.
- Taylor E. J. (2002). *Spiritual care: Nursing theory, research and practice*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Tuck, I. & Pullen, L. (1997). Spiritual Interventions Provided by Mental Health Nurses. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 19, 315 - 363.
- Winslow, G. R. & Winslow, B. W. (2003). Examining the ethnics of praying with patients. *Holistic Nursing Practice*. 17(4), 170 - 177.
- Wright, K. B. (1998). Clinical Scholarship: Professional, Ethical and Legal Implications for Spiritual Care in Nursing. *Image: The Journal of Nursing Scholarship* 30, 81 — 83.